

Hypoxis hemerocallidea Yellow Star

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Monocot

Size: 25 - 30 cm

Distribution:

The Yellow Star occurs in open grassland and woodland and is widespread in the eastern summer rainfall provinces of South Africa. It also occurs in Botswana, Lesotho and Swaziland.

Importance:

The species is a widely used medicinal plant in South Africa, well known for its immune-boosting properties. The rootstock is used to treat tuberculosis, urinary tract infections, prostate issues, rheumatoid arthritis and depression. Key compounds include hypoxoside, which converts to rooperol and sitosterol. However, raw forms contain toxic compounds. The species is heavily harvested, with unsustainable trade and habitat loss threatening the wild population. Conservation efforts are needed to protect this valuable species.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 201.63 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 16.05 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 4.96 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.8% [Single: 0.5%, Duplicated: 99.3%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 47 511.29 kilobases

Contig number: 1 489

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